

List of raw data files

Journal of Paper Conservation

FIXATIVE OR FINISH? IDENTIFYING THE SURFACE COATING ON JOHN CONSTABLE'S DRAWINGS
USING PEPTIDE MASS FINGERPRINTING

Daniel P. Kirby

John Slavin

"Boats on the River Severn at Worcester".txt

"Harrow from the Fields-" Eraser cube alone.txt

"Harrow from the Fields-" Scalpel and eraser cube.txt

"Worcester Cathedral from the Meadow".txt

63110 Salianski-Kremer Isinglass Glue.txt

Coleorton Hall recto.txt

Coleorton Hall verso, tuft sample.txt

Natural Sturgeon Fish Glue, Conservation Resources.txt

Russian sturgeon's glue Pushkin Moscow April '87.txt

Russian sturgeon's glue VNIIR Moscow April '87.txt

Sturgeon glue Hermitage Leningrad April '87.txt

TAD035001 Talas Sturgeon Glue.txt

Tate London TO8741- "Sketch of Shipping, Three Ships," 1803.txt

Tate London TO8742- "Sketch of Shipping, Three Ships, Close Hauled in a Choppy Sea," 1803.txt

Tate London TO8743- "Sketch of Shipping, Five Ships," 1803.txt